
ACCOUNTING ESTIMATE AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF QUOTED INDUSTRIAL GOODS MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study experimentally examined how accounting estimates affect the financial performance of Nigerian listed industrial products of manufacturing companies. Return on equity and return on assets served as proxies for financial success, while accounting estimates were assessed using provisions for depreciation, bad debt, and noncurrent assets. The study analysed data from 12 purposively selected companies out of 16 listed companies, covering audited financial reports from 2012 to 2022. Using ordinary least squares regression in EViews 10, the results showed that depreciation provisions had a positive but insignificant impact on return on equity while significantly influencing return on assets. Bad debt provisions positively and negligibly affected return on equity but significantly impacted return on assets. Noncurrent asset estimates positively and significantly influenced both return on equity and return on assets. The findings indicate that accounting estimates affect financial performance. The study recommends that companies adopt precise and cautious estimation techniques for depreciation, bad debt, and noncurrent assets. Financial managers and accountants should undergo regular training to improve accounting estimate implementation. Additionally, businesses should prioritise transparency in financial reporting to enhance reliability and investor confidence.

Keywords: Accounting estimates, financial performance, provision for depreciation, provision for bad debt, noncurrent asset estimate, return on equity, and return on assets.

Introduction

Financial statements serve as critical tools for assessing an entity's financial condition and operational results. Managers are responsible for preparing and fairly presenting these statements to reflect economic events and transactions accurately (IFRS Foundation, 2015). However, financial statements often rely on accounting estimates, which involve approximations where precise measurement is not available (American Institute of Certified Public Accountants, 2020). These estimates include provisions for depreciation, bad debts, inventory valuation, impairment losses, and retirement benefit obligations, among others (Nangih et al., 2021). Given their inherent subjectivity, accounting estimates require managerial judgement and are susceptible to biases, potentially impacting financial performance and decision-making (Dechow et al., 2010). The choice of estimation methods, such as FIFO versus LIFO for inventory valuation, can significantly affect reported earnings and financial ratios, influencing investor perceptions and market reactions (Hail et al., 2011).

The transparency and reliability of accounting estimates are crucial for maintaining investor confidence and regulatory compliance. Detailed disclosures regarding estimation methods help enhance trust, while frequent changes or inconsistencies can create uncertainty and negatively impact investor sentiment (Kothari et al., 2010). Regulatory bodies, such as the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), enforce stringent guidelines to ensure estimates accurately reflect a company's financial performance (Laux&Leuz, 2009). For example, the provision for depreciation impacts asset valuation and net income, while provisions for bad debts influence receivables and earnings stability (Godfrey & Espinosa, 2016; Lobo & Zhao, 2013). Additionally, impairment charges on noncurrent assets directly affect balance sheets and income statements, potentially altering investor assessments of long-term profitability (Barlev & Haddad, 2013).

Despite adherence to IFRS and Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP), the discretionary nature of accounting estimates introduces the risk of earnings management and financial misrepresentation (Raubenheimer, 2012). Estimates are often shaped by managerial experience and professional judgement, making financial statements a mix of historical data and predictive assumptions (IFRS Foundation, 2015). The increasing reliance on estimates highlights the ongoing debate between historical and fair value accounting, as financial reports are not exact depictions of financial reality but rather informed approximations (IASB, 2010). While necessary for financial reporting, accounting estimates must be carefully assessed to prevent distortions that could mislead stakeholders regarding a company's true financial health (Chukwu, 2006).

Statement of Problem

The accurate representation of a company's financial position through financial statements is essential for stakeholders, including investors, creditors, and regulatory bodies. Accounting estimates play a critical role in financial reporting by influencing perceived financial health and performance, particularly in the industrial goods sector, where companies face significant fluctuations in costs, inventory valuations, and asset depreciation (Penman, 2007; Lipe, 1990; Smith, 2015). In Nigeria, this sector significantly contributes to GDP and employment but operates within a volatile economic environment characterised by inflation, currency fluctuations, and regulatory inconsistencies (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2020). These factors complicate the process of making accurate accounting estimates, affecting financial statement reliability and, consequently, firm performance. Despite the significance of accounting

estimates in financial reporting, limited empirical research has examined their direct relationship with the financial performance of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Regulatory inconsistencies and varying levels of adherence to international financial reporting standards further exacerbate these challenges, emphasising the need for a comprehensive study on the implications of accounting estimates on financial performance within this sector (Adeyemi & Fagbemi, 2010).

This study aims to fill this research gap by investigating the extent to which accounting estimates impact the financial performance of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It will assess how these companies navigate estimation challenges, particularly in areas prone to significant uncertainties such as depreciation, inventory valuation, and bad debt provisions (Watts & Zimmerman, 1986; Dechow et al., 1995). Previous research has highlighted the broad impact of accounting estimates on financial reporting quality, yet there is a lack of studies specifically examining their methodologies and direct correlation with financial performance indicators in Nigeria (Jones, 2018; Okeke & Ezeabasili, 2019). Furthermore, compliance variability with International Financial Reporting Standards affects the comparability and reliability of financial statements, making it imperative to analyse the role of external auditors in ensuring accurate estimation practices (Adekoya, 2011; Carcello & Neal, 2000). This research will contribute to a deeper understanding of financial reporting practices in emerging economies, providing insights for regulators, auditors, corporate managers, and investors to enhance transparency, reliability, and financial statement comparability.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the relationship between Accounting Estimates and Financial Performance

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of accounting estimates on the financial performance of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Determine the effect of provision for depreciation on return on equity

- ii. Ascertain the effect of provision for depreciation on return on asset
- iii. Explore the effect of provision for bad debt on return on equity
- iv. Investigate the effect of provision for bad debt on return on asset
- v. Assess the effect of noncurrent asset estimate on return on equity
- vi. Ascertain the effect of noncurrent asset estimate on return on asset

Research questions

The following research questions were addressed:

- i. What is the effect of provision for depreciation on return on equity?
- ii. How does provision for depreciation affect return on asset?
- iii. What is the effect of provision for bad debt on return on equity?
- iv. How does provision for bad debt affect return on asset?
- v. What is the effect of noncurrent asset estimate on return on equity?
- vi. How does noncurrent asset estimate affect return on asset?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were tested:

- H01:** There is no significant effect of provision for depreciation on return on equity.
- H02:** There is no significant effect of provision for depreciation on return on asset.
- H03:** There is no significant effect of provision for bad debt on return on equity.
- H04:** There is no significant effect of provision for bad debt on return on asset.
- H05:** There is no significant effect of noncurrent asset estimate on return on equity.
- H06:** There is no significant effect of noncurrent asset estimate on return on asset.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant for corporate managers, investors, regulatory bodies, and scholars, as it provides insights into the role of accounting estimates in financial reporting, aiding strategic planning and resource allocation. Investors and analysts gain a understanding of estimation practices and financial risk, while regulatory bodies can refine financial reporting standards to enhance transparency and compliance. Additionally, the research contributes to academic literature by bridging knowledge gaps on accounting estimates and financial

performance in emerging economies, fostering interdisciplinary research in corporate finance, accounting, and economic policy.

Conceptual Review

Accounting estimates involve management judgements and assumptions to approximate financial statement items that lack precise measurement (Kieso et al., 2019; Horngren et al., 2020; Weygandt et al., 2020). These estimates, including provisions for depreciation, debts, asset impairments, and contingent liabilities, significantly impact financial performance by influencing income, expenses, and key financial ratios (IASB, 2009; FASB, ASC 330; IAS 36). The reliability of accounting estimates depends on the quality of available information, management's judgement, and compliance with financial reporting standards, raising concerns about estimation uncertainty, potential bias, and ethical considerations (IESBA, Code of Ethics; PCAOB, AS 2501). Regulatory frameworks, such as IFRS 9 and ASC 842, seek to enhance transparency and comparability, while advancements in artificial intelligence and big data analytics improve estimation accuracy (Deloitte, 2021; IFRS Foundation, IFRS 15; FASB, ASC 606). Additionally, corporate governance structures, including audit committees, play a crucial role in ensuring unbiased estimates, particularly in light of sustainability and ESG reporting trends that require new estimation frameworks (SEC, MD&A Guidance; Sarbanes-Oxley Act).

Provision for Depreciation

Non-current and intangible assets such as property, plant, and equipment; development costs; goodwill; and intellectual property provide economic benefits beyond the current financial year and are capitalised rather than expensed, with costs allocated over their useful lives per IAS 16 (International Accounting Standard). Depreciation methods, such as the straight-line and reducing balance methods, must align with the pattern of economic benefits consumed and be reviewed annually (IAS 16). Studies by Mert and Dil (2016) and Indrayani (2018) indicate that depreciation methods significantly impact financial performance and profitability. Depreciation influences net income, tax liabilities, and cash flow by reducing taxable income and improving reinvestment capacity (Horngren et al., 2014; Damodaran, 2012). Strategic depreciation management affects capital expenditure planning, operational efficiency, and long-term growth (Brealey et al., 2020). Compliance with IFRS and GAAP ensures transparency and comparability, while evolving standards and sustainability considerations impact asset valuation and depreciation practices (Nobes & Parker, 2016). Technological advancements necessitate dynamic depreciation strategies to reflect asset obsolescence and maintain financial accuracy (Epstein & Jermakowicz, 2017).

Provision for Bad Debt

Proper recognition of revenues and expenses necessitates recording bad debts as expenses in the period revenue is earned rather than when the company writes off the amounts (Kieso et al., 2012). The provision for bad debts, or allowance for doubtful accounts, is crucial for financial accuracy, impacting net income, cash flow, and decision-making (Warren et al., 2018). It ensures realistic profitability reporting by anticipating potential credit losses, which aids in cash flow planning and liquidity management (Ross et al., 2019). Companies estimate bad debts based on historical data, economic conditions, and customer creditworthiness, supporting informed credit policies and risk management (Brigham & Houston, 2013). Accounting standards like IFRS 9 and GAAP's ASC 326 require a forward-looking approach to credit loss estimation, ensuring accurate financial reporting (IFRS Foundation; FASB). Additionally, predictive analytics improves provision accuracy, affecting investor perceptions

and financial transparency, though ethical concerns exist regarding earnings manipulation (Delen et al., 2013; Ronald et al., 2011). The evolving regulatory environment underscores the importance of robust risk assessment, adapting to economic shifts, and complying with global standards (Laux & Leuz, 2009).

Non-Current Assets Estimates

Intangible assets, such as goodwill and trademarks, are non-monetary and lack physical form, requiring reliable estimates for measurement and recognition (IAS 38). These assets are recorded when future economic benefits are probable, with cost and revaluation models available for subsequent valuation (Chukwu, 2006). Studies show mixed findings on the relationship between intangible assets and market value, with some confirming a positive impact (Oliveria et al., 2010; Abubakar & Abubakar, 2015) and others finding no significant correlation (Ely & Waymire, 1999). Depreciation, amortization, and impairment estimates significantly influence asset valuation and financial performance, impacting key financial ratios (Penman, 2013). IFRS and GAAP mandate periodic impairment assessments to ensure non-current assets accurately reflect their recoverable amounts, which is particularly crucial in volatile industries (Kieso et al., 2013). These estimates also affect strategic investment decisions, influencing capital budgeting techniques such as NPV and IRR (Brealey et al., 2020). Advances in technology, such as AI and IoT, enhance asset estimation accuracy, supporting better depreciation schedules and maintenance strategies (Tysiac, 2016). In mergers and acquisitions, asset valuation adjustments affect post-acquisition financial performance, requiring precise fair value assessments (Damodaran, 2010). Economic downturns and regulatory shifts often necessitate revisions in asset estimates, impacting financial reporting and strategic planning (Laux & Leuz, 2009). Sustainability concerns further shape asset valuations, as regulatory pressures and consumer preferences drive changes in depreciation and impairment practices (Eccles & Krzus, 2010).

Financial Performance

Using measurements like return on equity, return on assets, profit margins, and liquidity ratios, financial performance is a thorough assessment of a company's total financial health, profitability, and efficiency (Brigham & Houston, 2019; Gitman & Zutter, 2019). It shows how well a company can use its resources to make money from its primary business (Brealey et al., 2020; Weygandt et al., 2020). Insights into profitability, solvency, and liquidity are provided by key financial statements, such as the cash flow statement, balance sheet, and income statement, which assist stakeholders in making well-informed decisions (Ross et al., 2019; Penman, 2013). By influencing reported earnings, asset values, and financial ratios, accounting assumptions like depreciation techniques, inventory valuation, and bad debt provisions have a big impact on financial performance (Horngren et al., 2020; Weygandt et al., 2020). By influencing operational effectiveness, risk management, and long-term value creation, external factors such as market conditions, corporate governance, sustainability initiatives, and technological advancements also influence financial performance (Shapiro, 2015; Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Eccles et al., 2014). Through cost reduction, improved reputation, and competitive advantage, businesses that use digital transformation and robust ESG policies frequently see improvements in their financial performance (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014; Kaplan & Norton, 1992). As a result, financial performance goes beyond conventional measurements, taking into account both quantitative and qualitative elements that affect a company's long-term viability and prosperity.

Return on Assets (ROA)

Return on Assets (ROA), which is computed as net income divided by total assets and shown as a percentage, gauges how well a business uses its assets to produce profit (Brealey et al., 2020). Because it aids in determining investment returns, it is essential for assessing financial performance, especially in capital-intensive sectors (Horngren et al., 2020). Investors use ROA to compare companies within the same industry, with a consistently high ROA indicating strong financial management (Brigham & Houston, 2019). However, ROA has limitations, as capital-intensive industries may have lower figures without indicating poor management (Kieso et al., 2018). Asset valuation and depreciation methods affect comparability, though IFRS and GAAP ensure consistency in financial reporting. Strategic financial decisions, such as asset optimisation, focus on improving ROA to enhance competitiveness (Brigham & Ehrhardt, 2016). ROA varies across industries due to capital intensity, with technology and service companies typically having higher ROA than manufacturing or utilities (Damodaran, 2012). Economic cycles influence ROA, as expansions improve asset utilisation while downturns reduce sales and increase idle assets (Acharya et al., 2012). Digital transformation, through big data and AI, has enhanced ROA analysis by providing predictive insights into asset performance and financial health (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2014).

Return on Equity (ROE)

Return on Equity (ROE), which is computed as net income divided by shareholder equity and shown as a percentage, gauges a company's capacity to make money off of investments made by shareholders (Brealey et al., 2020). In addition to indicating the effect of financial leverage on profitability, a higher ROE denotes efficient management and efficient use of equity capital (Brigham & Houston, 2019). According to Weygandt et al. (2020), ROE is frequently used to compare performance both within and between industries, offering valuable information on financial health and investment appeal. However, high debt levels can artificially inflate ROE, masking operational inefficiencies, while intangible assets and capital-intensive industries may distort figures, necessitating industry benchmarks for accurate analysis (Horngren et al., 2020; Penman, 2013). By breaking down ROE into financial leverage, asset turnover, and profit margin, the DuPont analysis provides a deeper understanding of its determinants (Kieso et al., 2018). According to Acharya et al. (2012), economic cycles have an impact on ROE; expansions boost profitability while downturns lower profits. Companies manage ROE through strategic financial decisions, including debt.

Empirical Review

Abubakar and Olowe (2019) examined how trade receivables affected the performance of a few Nigerian listed companies. Ten (10) companies that were listed on the Nigerian stock exchange between 2012 and 2018 make up the population, which was chosen through the use of purposive sampling. To test the developed hypotheses, the study used the multiple regressions approach. While return on equity was used to gauge business success, the dimensions for accounts receivable were revenue growth, debt ratio, and accounts receivable ratio. The analysis's findings demonstrated that revenue growth, the debt-to-accounts-receivable ratio, and these factors all significantly improved the success of the company.

Anastasia et al. (2014) investigated the corporate performance and accounts receivable management of Nigerian food and beverage industries. Sales growth, debt, and accounts receivable served as the study's independent variables. Data from secondary sources were used between 2000 and 2011. The test of hypotheses was examined using multiple regression. The study found that whereas debt and sales growth had a positive but negligible association with the profitability of Nigerian food and beverage manufacturing enterprises, accounts receivable had a negative but negligible link with profitability.

Anichebe and Nangih (2021) assessed the effects of accounting estimates on information misstatements of financial reports of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria. The study employed a survey design. They examined the impacts of depreciation estimates, impairment loss, inventory estimates, goodwill estimates and estimated useful life of assets on financial reports. The findings revealed that wrong estimates may lead to, but are not the only cause of, misstatements in financial reports.

Bawa et al. (2018) investigated how inventory management affected the business performance of Ghanaian manufacturing enterprises that were listed. 140 firm-year observations from 14 manufacturing companies listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE) across a ten-year period, from 2007 to 2016, comprised the sample, which was derived using cross-sectional secondary data. Multiple regression analysis and Pearson correlation were used to test the acquired data. The empirical results showed that the performance of the company was unaffected by inventory management. The outcome demonstrated that, during the time period, there was no significant relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Belsoi et al. (2017) evaluated how estimations affected Kenyan microfinance enterprises' performance. Ninety-three (93) individuals from three distinct strata—account officers, internal auditors, and management—of the 14 microfinance organisations made up the research population. According to their findings, the financial performance of microfinance organisations and the independent variable (assets estimation) have a positive but highly significant association. Additionally, it found a strong inverse relationship between financial success and the assessment of an asset's usable life.

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The impact of non-current assets, such as property, plant and equipment, on the corporate performance of Nigerian manufacturing companies was investigated by Chukwu and Egbuhuzor (2017). Ten manufacturing businesses that were listed on the stock exchange provided financial statement data for the research, which employed return on equity and return on assets to gauge company performance. Multiple regression analysis results showed a strong and favourable correlation between return on assets and plant and machinery. Nevertheless, there was a negative correlation between return on assets and land and buildings. As a result, the study concluded that investments in tangible noncurrent assets had an impact on businesses' profitability.

Gamayuni (2015) investigated the impact of financial performance, financial policies, and intangible assets on the firm value of Indonesian businesses. The study's empirical goal was to determine how Indonesian organisations' financial performance, financial policies, and intangible assets relate to one another. Between 2007 and 2009, path analysis was used to determine how the variables related to one another. This study discovered that financial performance, financial policies, and intangible assets all significantly impacted business value at the same time. Additionally, it was discovered that intangible assets had a positive and substantial link with financial performance as determined by ROA and company value but had no discernible impact on financial policies. ROA and debt policies have a favourable and large impact on business value.

Ganyam and Ivungu (2019) evaluated how accounting information systems affected businesses' financial performance. The study's specific goal was to evaluate the theoretical and conceptual challenges surrounding accounting information systems and how they relate to businesses' financial success. The review's findings demonstrated the impact of accounting data on financial performance. The study also discovered that while the majority of previous studies used the survey research design to look at the links, most of them were conducted in developed economies rather than in less developed ones like Nigeria.

Gap in Literature

The connection between accounting estimates and financial performance in Nigeria and other developing nations has been the subject of several studies. Trade receivables, fair value measurement, depreciation, and non-current assets have all been studied in relation to company performance, profitability, and the calibre of financial reporting. Although earlier research has concentrated on a number of industries, none have explicitly examined how accounting assumptions affect the financial performance of publicly traded industrial products manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The current study uses ordinary least squares regression, as opposed to previous research that used correlation and multiple regression. Financial performance is measured by return on equity and return on assets, while accounting estimates are proxied by provisions for depreciation, bad debt, and non-current asset estimates.

Methodology

As of February 28, 2024, sixteen quoted industrial products manufacturing companies that are listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group make up the study's population. To ensure that findings may be applied throughout the industry, the population is representative of all groups important to the study (Etikan et al., 2016; Baridam, 2004; Cooper & Schindler, 2011). Twelve (12) of the listed industrial products manufacturing enterprises were chosen for the study's sample size using a purposive and judgemental sampling approach throughout a ten-year period from 2012 to 2022. Because data for all 16 of the listed industrial products manufacturing companies in Nigeria are incomplete or partially unavailable, the study uses the purposive sampling approach. The ten (10) year timeframe was selected to ensure that the financial data accessible is current, fair, reasonable, and dependable. The Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX Group) and the sample of listed industrial products manufacturing companies in Nigeria's annual financial reports from 2012 to 2012–2022 serve as the study's primary data sources. The annual financial reports of listed Nigerian industry products manufacturing companies from 2012 to 2022 would be the source of the secondary data. Descriptive and instrumental statistics are also used in the study, as are inferential statistics that draw

conclusions or forecasts about a population from a sample of data. covers regression analysis and hypothesis testing.

Model Specification

The conceptual framework shows the relationship between accounting estimates and financial performance and its proxies. Accounting estimate is proxied by provision for depreciation, provision for bad debt and non-current asset estimate, while financial performance is proxied by return on equity and return on asset.

The Functional Relationship of Independent and Dependent Variable of the study is shown below;

Function:

$$FPF=f(ACE) \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

$$FPF = \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 ACE + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

Functional Relationship

$$ROE= f(PFD, PBD, NCA) \dots\dots\dots (3.3)$$

$$ROA= f(PFD, PBD, NCA) \dots\dots\dots (3.4)$$

Model Specification

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PFD_{it} + \beta_2 PBD + \beta_3 NCA_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots (3.7)$$

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PFD_{it} + \beta_2 PBD + \beta_3 NCA_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots (3.8)$$

Where

- ACE = Accounting Estimate
- FPF = Financial Performance
- PFD = Provision for Depreciation
- PBD = Provision for Bad Debt
- NCA = Noncurrent Asset Estimate
- ROE = Return on Equity
- ROA = Return on Asset
- $\alpha_1 - \alpha_4$ = Slope
- $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Regression Coefficient
- α = Regression Constant
- ϵ_{it} = Error Term

Data Analysis
Bivariate Data Analysis
Test of Hypothesis 1

H_{01} : There is no significant effect of provision for depreciation on return on equity of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Table 1: Regression Result of Provision for Depreciation and Return on Equity

Dependent Variable: ROE
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 08/30/24 Time: 17:25
 Sample: 2012 2022
 Included observations: 132

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.469741	0.249923	1.879541	0.0624
PFD	0.085800	2.892979	0.029658	0.9764
R-squared	0.800007	Mean dependent var		0.474368
Adjusted R-squared	0.707685	S.D. dependent var		2.234922
S.E. of regression	2.243494	Akaike info criterion		4.468981
Sum squared resid	654.3243	Schwarz criterion		4.512660
Log likelihood	292.9528	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.486730
F-statistic	0.000880	Durbin-Watson stat		2.064925
Prob(F-statistic)	0.976385			

The regression analysis in Table 1 examines the effect of provision for depreciation on return on equity (ROE) for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The coefficient for provision for depreciation is 0.0858, suggesting a positive but weak relationship with ROE. However, the P-value of 0.9764 is much higher than the 0.05 significance level, indicating that this relationship is not statistically significant. Despite an R-squared value of 80.00%, which suggests a strong model fit, the adjusted R-squared (70.77%) and the high Prob(F-statistic) (0.9764) indicate that provision for depreciation does not significantly explain variations in ROE. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.0649 suggests no autocorrelation in the residuals, confirming the validity of the regression model. Given these findings, the null hypothesis that provision for depreciation has no significant effect on ROE—is supported, implying that other factors, beyond depreciation-related accounting estimates, play a more significant role in determining ROE for industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis 2

H₀₂: There is no significant effect of provision for depreciation on return on asset of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Table 2: Regression Result of Provision for Depreciation and Return on Asset

Dependent Variable: ROA

Method: Least Squares

Date: 08/30/24 Time: 17:26

Sample: 2012 2022

Included observations: 132

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.113725	0.024575	4.627570	0.0000
FPD	0.253127	0.284472	0.889814	0.0152
R-squared	0.906054	Mean dependent var		0.127373
Adjusted R-squared	0.801592	S.D. dependent var		0.220432
S.E. of regression	0.220607	Akaike info criterion		0.169833
Sum squared resid	6.326766	Schwarz criterion		0.126154
Log likelihood	13.20896	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.152084
F-statistic	0.791769	Durbin-Watson stat		2.036083
Prob(F-statistic)	0.015210			

The regression analysis in Table 2 examines the effect of provision for depreciation on return on assets (ROA) for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The coefficient of 0.2531 suggests a positive relationship, indicating that an increase in provision for depreciation is associated with a higher ROA. With a P-value of 0.0152 (below 0.05), this effect is statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The high R-squared value (90.61%) and adjusted R-squared (80.16%) indicate that provision for depreciation explains a significant portion of the variation in ROA. Additionally, the low Prob(F-statistic) (0.0152) accompanies the overall model's significance. The Durbin-Watson statistic (2.0361) suggests no autocorrelation, ensuring the validity of the results. These findings suggest that companies with higher depreciation provisions may be managing their assets more effectively, leading to improved financial performance. Overall, the study highlights the importance of accounting estimates, particularly depreciation, in influencing ROA for industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis 3

H₀₃: There is no significant effect of provision for bad debt on return on equity of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Table 3: Regression Result of Provision for Bad Debt and Return on Equity

Dependent Variable: ROE
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 08/30/24 Time: 17:27
 Sample: 2012 2022
 Included observations: 132

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.500360	0.201052	2.488716	0.0141
PBD	4.564311	8.551311	0.533475	0.4946
R-squared	0.702184	Mean dependent var		0.474368
Adjusted R-squared	0.605491	S.D. dependent var		2.234922
S.E. of regression	2.241050	Akaike info criterion		4.466801
Sum squared resid	652.8994	Schwarz criterion		4.510480
Log likelihood	292.8089	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.484550
F-statistic	0.284595	Durbin-Watson stat		2.006701
Prob(F-statistic)	0.494616			

The regression analysis in Table 3 examines the effect of provision for debt on return on equity (ROE) for quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The coefficient of 4.5643 suggests a potential positive relationship; however, the high P-value (0.4946) indicates that this effect is not statistically significant, leading to the failure to reject the null hypothesis. Despite an R-squared value of 70.22%, which suggests that a large portion of ROE variability is explained by the model, the lack of significance weakens the reliability of this relationship. The adjusted R-squared (60.55%) further accompanies that the inclusion of a provision for bad debt does not significantly enhance the model's explanatory power. Additionally, the high Prob(F-statistic) (0.4946) shows that the overall model is not statistically significant. The Durbin-Watson statistic (2.0067) suggests no autocorrelation, ensuring the validity of the results. These findings imply that provision for bad debt does not significantly impact ROE, suggesting that other factors outside of accounting estimates like bad debt provisions may play a more substantial role in influencing financial performance in this sector.

Test of Hypothesis 4

H₀₄: There is no significant effect of provision for bad debt on return on asset of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Table 4: Regression Result of Provision for Bad Debt and Return on Asset

Dependent Variable: ROA

Method: Least Squares

Date: 08/30/24 Time: 17:28

Sample: 2012 2022

Included observations: 132

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.133231	0.019738	6.749976	0.0000
PBD	1.036711	8.391242	1.224703	0.0229
R-squared	0.811406	Mean dependent var		0.127373
Adjusted R-squared	0.703802	S.D. dependent var		0.220432
S.E. of regression	0.220012	Akaike info criterion		0.175232
Sum squared resid	6.292696	Schwarz criterion		0.131553
Log likelihood	13.56533	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.157483
F-statistic	1.499897	Durbin-Watson stat		2.071360
Prob(F-statistic)	0.022902			

The regression analysis in Table 4 examines the effect of provision for bad debt on return on assets (ROA) for quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The coefficient of 1.0367 suggests a positive relationship, indicating that an increase in provision for bad debt is associated with a rise in ROA. The P-value (0.0229) is below 0.05, confirming statistical significance and leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The high R-squared value (81.14%) suggests that provision for bad debt explains a substantial portion of ROA variability, while the adjusted R-squared (70.38%) indicates strong explanatory power even after adjusting for additional variables. The significant Prob (F-statistic) (0.0229) accompanies the model's overall validity, and the Durbin-Watson statistic (2.0714) suggests no significant autocorrelation, ensuring result reliability. These findings imply that companies with higher provisions for bad debt may be managing receivables more effectively, leading to improved asset utilisation and financial performance. Thus, accounting estimates, particularly bad debt provisions, play a crucial role in influencing ROA in Nigeria's industrial goods manufacturing sector.

Test of Hypothesis 5

H₀₅: There is no significant effect of noncurrent asset estimate on return on equity of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Table 5: Regression Result of Noncurrent Asset Estimate and Return on Equity

Dependent Variable: ROE

Method: Least Squares

Date: 08/30/24 Time: 17:29

Sample: 2012 2022

Included observations: 132

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.498271	0.416663	1.195862	0.2339
NCA	0.043301	0.666757	0.064943	0.0483
R-squared	0.900032	Mean dependent var		0.474368
Adjusted R-squared	0.807660	S.D. dependent var		2.234922
S.E. of regression	2.243465	Akaike info criterion		4.468956
Sum squared resid	654.3075	Schwarz criterion		4.512634
Log likelihood	292.9511	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.486705
F-statistic	0.004218	Durbin-Watson stat		2.064350
Prob(F-statistic)	0.048319			

The regression analysis in Table 5 examines the effect of noncurrent asset estimates on return on equity (ROE) for quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The coefficient of 0.0433 suggests a positive relationship, indicating that an increase in noncurrent asset estimates is associated with a rise in ROE. The P-value (0.0483) is slightly below 0.05, confirming statistical significance and leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The high R-squared value (90.00%) suggests that noncurrent asset estimates explain a substantial portion of ROE variability, while the adjusted R-squared (80.77%) indicates strong explanatory power even after adjusting for additional variables. The significant Prob(F-statistic) (0.0483) accompanies the model's overall validity, and the Durbin-Watson statistic (2.0644) suggests no significant autocorrelation, ensuring result reliability. These findings imply that companies with higher noncurrent asset estimates may be perceived as having stronger asset bases, positively influencing profitability and shareholder returns. Thus, accounting estimates, particularly noncurrent asset valuation, play a crucial role in determining ROE in Nigeria's industrial goods manufacturing sector.

Test of Hypothesis 6

H₀₆: There is no significant effect of noncurrent asset estimate on return on asset of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Table 6: Regression Result of Noncurrent Asset Estimate and Return on Asset

Dependent Variable: ROA

Method: Least Squares

Date: 08/30/24 Time: 17:31

Sample: 2012 2022

Included observations: 132

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.254308	0.039116	6.501323	0.0000
NCA	0.229940	0.062595	3.673448	0.0003
R-squared	0.894040	Mean dependent var		0.127373
Adjusted R-squared	0.787071	S.D. dependent var		0.220432
S.E. of regression	0.210616	Akaike info criterion		0.262521
Sum squared resid	5.766705	Schwarz criterion		0.218842
Log likelihood	19.32638	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.244772
F-statistic	13.49422	Durbin-Watson stat		2.003491
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000348			

The regression analysis in Table 6 examines the effect of noncurrent asset estimates on return on assets (ROA) for quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The coefficient of 0.2299 suggests a positive relationship, indicating that an increase in noncurrent asset estimates is associated with a rise in ROA. The P-value (0.0003) is significantly below 0.05, confirming statistical significance and leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The high R-squared value (89.40%) suggests that noncurrent asset estimates explain a substantial portion of ROA variability, while the adjusted R-squared (78.71%) indicates strong explanatory power even after adjusting for additional variables. The significant Prob(F-statistic) (0.0003) accompanies the model's overall validity, and the Durbin-Watson statistic (2.0035) suggests no significant autocorrelation, ensuring result reliability. These findings imply that companies with higher noncurrent asset estimates may be more efficient in utilising their assets to generate returns, reflecting strong asset management practices. Thus, accounting estimates, particularly noncurrent asset valuation, play a crucial role in determining ROA in Nigeria's industrial goods manufacturing sector.

Discussion of Findings

H_{A1}: There is a significant effect of provision for depreciation on return on equity of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The regression analysis reveals that provision for depreciation has no significant impact on return on equity (ROE) in quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria, as indicated by a high P-value (0.9764). Despite an R-squared value of 80.00%, suggesting a strong model fit, the lack of statistical significance implies that other factors influence ROE more than depreciation estimates. This aligns with Anichebe and Nangih (2021), who found that accounting estimates contribute to, but are not the sole cause of, financial report misstatements. From an Information Asymmetry Theory perspective, managers have superior

financial knowledge over investors, potentially influencing market perceptions and decision-making. Additionally, companies may manipulate accounting estimates to present a more favorable financial position, affecting investor confidence. In Nigeria's regulatory environment, where oversight varies, such asymmetry is more pronounced. Signaling theory suggests that managers use estimates to convey financial prudence or expected growth, shaping market reactions. Overall, the findings suggest that depreciation estimates are not a key determinant of ROE, and decision-makers should explore other significant financial performance drivers.

H_{A2}: There is a significant effect of provision for depreciation on return on asset of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The regression results indicate a significant positive relationship between provision for depreciation and return on assets, suggesting that depreciation accounting influences the financial performance of industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This aligns with Anichebe and Nangih (2021), who found that accounting estimates contribute to financial misstatements, and Nangih et al. (2021), who highlighted the overall significance of accounting estimates in predicting financial performance, though individual estimates like depreciation showed non-significant effects. Anchoring this study on Agency Theory is relevant, as it explains how managers (agents) may manipulate accounting estimates to serve personal interests, creating conflicts with shareholders (principals). Information asymmetry and agency costs further complicate monitoring managerial actions, emphasising the need for strong corporate governance mechanisms, such as independent boards and external audits, to ensure financial statements reflect true performance. Understanding how incentive structures influence managerial discretion in accounting estimates is crucial for mitigating potential misrepresentation in Nigeria's industrial sector.

H_{A3}: There is a significant effect of provision for bad debt on return on equity of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The regression results indicate that provision for bad debt does not significantly impact return on equity for industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria, as evidenced by a P-value of 0.4946, which exceeds the 0.05 significance threshold. Despite an R-squared value of 70.22%, suggesting that independent variables explain a substantial portion of the variance in return on equity, the lack of statistical significance undermines its predictive power. This finding aligns with Ayunku and Eweke (2017), who found that accounting estimates influence financial reporting quality but emphasized the need for harmonized accounting standards. Anchoring this study on Positive Accounting Theory provides insight into why managers choose specific accounting estimates based on incentives such as bonus plans, debt covenants, regulatory pressures, and political costs. The theory explains how economic conditions, contractual obligations, and external scrutiny shape accounting choices, impacting financial performance. In Nigeria's industrial goods manufacturing sector, understanding these motivations is crucial for evaluating financial reporting accuracy and ensuring transparency in managerial decision-making.

H_{A4}: There is a significant effect of provision for bad debt on return on asset of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Our study aligns with Belsoi et al. (2017), who found a significant relationship between asset estimation and financial performance in Kenyan microfinance companies, and with Peter and

Gamaliel (2019), who revealed that increased accounting estimates (provisions for bad debt and depreciation) lead to greater accounting discretion and lower financial reporting quality in Nigerian banks. These findings emphasise the need for harmonised accounting standards to ensure transparency and consistency in financial reporting. Anchoring this study on Positive Accounting Theory provides a framework for understanding managerial accounting choices influenced by incentives such as bonuses, debt covenants, and regulatory pressures. The theory helps predict how managers in Nigeria's industrial goods manufacturing sector adjust accounting estimates in response to economic and regulatory changes, shaping financial performance. It also highlights the role of external pressures, such as political costs and regulatory scrutiny, in financial reporting, reinforcing the importance of standardised accounting practices to maintain credibility and market confidence.

H_{A5}: There is a significant effect of noncurrent asset estimate on return on equity of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Our study reveals a significant positive relationship between noncurrent asset estimates and return on equity (ROE) in Nigeria's industrial goods manufacturing sector, with a P-value of 0.0483, an R-squared value of 90%, and an adjusted R-squared of 80.77%, indicating strong model fit. These findings align with Idatoru et al. (2021), who found that accounting estimates negatively impact profitability in Nigeria's consumer goods sector, emphasising the need for IFRS compliance and robust external audit scrutiny. Anchoring this study on Agency Theory provides a framework for understanding how managers (agents) may manipulate accounting estimates to enhance short-term financial performance, often at the expense of shareholder (principal) interests. The theory highlights information asymmetry, agency costs, and managerial discretion in accounting choices, underscoring the importance of corporate governance mechanisms such as independent boards, audit committees, and external audits to ensure transparency. Additionally, the study examines how performance-based incentives influence managerial decisions regarding accounting estimates, further reinforcing the necessity of aligning managerial incentives with long-term shareholder value to ensure accurate financial reporting.

H_{A6}: There is a significant effect of noncurrent asset estimate on return on asset of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Our study finds a significant positive relationship between noncurrent asset estimates and return on assets (ROA) in Nigeria's industrial goods manufacturing sector, with a P-value of 0.0003 and an R-squared value of 89.40%, indicating strong explanatory power. These results align with Belsoi et al. (2017), who found a significant relationship between asset estimation and financial performance in Kenyan microfinance companies. Anchoring this study on Information Asymmetry Theory highlights how managers, having superior knowledge of accounting estimates and financial performance, can influence investor perceptions and decision-making. Information asymmetry may lead to adverse selection and moral hazard, where managers manipulate estimates to present a more favorable financial position, potentially misleading investors. In Nigeria's emerging market, where regulatory oversight varies, this asymmetry is more pronounced, making transparency in accounting estimates crucial. Additionally, signaling theory suggests that companies use conservative or aggressive estimates to communicate financial stability or expected growth. Understanding these dynamics underscores the need for strong corporate governance to ensure reliable financial reporting and investor confidence.

Conclusion

This study examined the effect of accounting estimates on the financial performance of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria, using provision for depreciation, provision for bad debt, and noncurrent asset estimates as key variables. Findings reveal that noncurrent asset estimates had a positive and significant impact on both return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA), while provision for depreciation significantly influenced ROA but not ROE. Provision for debt had a significant effect on ROA but was insignificant for ROE. These results emphasise the importance of prudent accounting estimates in enhancing financial stability and profitability, reinforcing the need for accurate and conservative accounting practices to improve transparency and financial performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the research study on accounting estimates and financial performance of quoted industrial goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. Companies should ensure the use of accurate and conservative methods for estimating provisions for depreciation, provisions for bad debt, and noncurrent asset estimates will improve the reliability of financial statements and better reflect the true financial position of the firm, thereby enhancing investor confidence and decision-making.
- ii. Regular training programmes should be provided for accountants and financial managers to improve their skills in applying accounting estimates. This will ensure that estimates are consistently applied according to best practices and accounting standards, reducing errors and discrepancies in financial reporting.
- iii. Companies should establish robust internal controls and governance mechanisms to oversee the accounting estimation process. This includes regular audits and reviews of the methods and assumptions used in calculating provisions for depreciation, bad debt, and noncurrent assets to ensure accuracy and compliance with relevant accounting standards.
- iv. Transparency in financial reporting should be a priority for companies. Clear and detailed disclosures about the methods and assumptions used in accounting estimates should be provided in financial statements. will help reduce information asymmetry and provide stakeholders with a better understanding of the firm's financial performance.
- v. Companies should invest in advanced accounting software and digital tools that automate and enhance the accuracy of accounting estimates. The adoption of innovative technologies can streamline the accounting process, reduce manual errors, and improve the timeliness and accuracy of financial reporting.
- vi. Accounting policies related to estimates should be regularly reviewed and updated to reflect changes in the business environment, regulatory requirements, and industry practices. This will ensure that accounting estimates remain relevant and accurate, helping companies maintain compliance and provide accurate financial information.

- vii. Companies should implement effective risk management practices to monitor and manage potential financial risks associated with accounting estimates. This includes assessing the impact of changes in market conditions or operational factors on depreciation, bad debt, and asset valuations to proactively address any adverse effects on financial performance.

- viii. Companies should collaborate with regulatory bodies to ensure that accounting estimates are in line with the latest standards and regulations. This collaboration can help companies stay updated on changes in accounting rules and adopt best practices in financial reporting.

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